

Performance assessment of advanced materials in architectural envelopes

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Business

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ADVANCED
BUILDING SKINS

From the lab to the crane

A long process to ensure the desired performance in the upscaling process.

Development steps

- Evolution from an initial idea, and key performance level towards assessing all critical issues for construction products.
 - Key performance indicators (Insulation materials): thermal conductivity, fire behavior,...
 - Other performances: Dimensional stability, planitude,...
 - Industry standards/quality levels, customer expectations
 - Specific needs as prescribed by national/local/municipal regulations,...

Specification - Assessment cycle

Technology readiness level

- Various systems have been developed
- Assess the maturity of a technology related to its market implementation
- In EU, TRL scale

Technology readiness level

Technology hybridation

- Commercially available material/systems for other applications is not necessarily directly suitable for the construction sector
 - Long life span
 - Exposure to external conditions, solar radiation,...
 - In thermal systems, relatively small interactions but for longer periods, inertia,...
- Previous experiences need to be carefully addressed for a new technology roadmap

e.g. adaptation of PCM systems

Comercially available PCM
Thermal wave attenuation in
portable cooled devices

Integration in building
envelopes

CASE1: HEMPSEC

- **BACKGROUND**

- Prefabricated timber frame assembly with natural insulation materials.
- Already in use in UK.
- Experiences with HEMP in many countries and niche markets in EU.

- **PRESENT DEVELOPMENT**

- Certification of the system
- Improvement of the drying process
- Full scale assessment

CASE1: HEMPSEC

- Assessment

- Thermal insulation capacity
- Presence of thermal bridges
- Thermal buffering capacity
- Moisture buffering capacity

...Under full scale conditions

- Prescribed activities

 – Drying testbench & laboratory tests (U. Bath)

– Full scale assessment at the Kubik by Tecnalia test facility.

CASE 1: HEMPSEC

CASE2: AEROCOINS

- **BACKGROUND**

- Aerogel-based construction product at laboratory scale (10x10x1cm samples)
- Upscaled by means of semi-industrial process.
- Integrated into a dry framing system.

- **DEVELOPMENT**

- Performance needs to be kept in the upscaling process
- High quality thermal integration in framing system
- Fire performance

CASE2: AEROCOINS

- Design & Assessment activities
 - Thermal bridge assessment: Avoid metal and wood framed elements.
 - Substitute by plastic composite frames.
 - Full scale thermal assessment.
 - Thermal resistance
 - Thermal bridges (IR camera)
 - Fire reaction tests (SBI)

CASE2: AEROCOINS

Temperature
Relative Humidity
Heat flux

Conclusions

- Critical product development needs:
 - Assess the technological status for each particular intended use
 - Evaluate all relevant information from earlier steps
 - Close information exchange with suppliers in product/material integration schemes
 - Know the requirements of development
 - Intended use
 - Unique selling point, market advantage against competing technologies

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